

The Study on Challenges Faced by the Women Weaver's in Udupi Taluk

Ashalatha K* & Sudeep Devadiga

Department of Management, Justice K S Hegde Institute of Management, Nitte

Abstract:

The handloom business is producing jobs at all stages of farming, raising, and weaving. It has made a tremendous impact to the socioeconomic lives of people, particularly women. However, it has recently been observed that, as a result of globalization and changing market needs, this industry is in turmoil, facing detrimental effects from government policies and discriminatory competitors, as well as piracy in product quality. Women's empowerment is a critical instrument for bringing about changes in their socioeconomic status. Weaving is an important source of revenue for the residents of Udupi. The goal of this study is to examine how this field affects women's empowerment and the economic situation of female weavers. A qualitative research technique adapted with primary data gathering processes such as questionnaires, surveys and personal interviews was utilised to investigate information from 100 samples of women weavers in Udupi. Data were analysed using Microsoft Excel in a detailed manner utilising graphs, charts, and diagrams. Henry Garret ranking Technique has been used to rank the challenges faced by women weavers in Udupi District. The findings show that the women weavers of Udupi are rising at a rapid pace and empowering themselves via their job, and that women are strengthening themselves economically through the weaving sector. At the same time, they confront obstacles like raw material availability, lack of demand, work-life balance, health issues, traditional stereotypes, marketing problems, and a lack of income during the off-season. Among the aforementioned concerns, health issues are regarded as the most serious issue confronting women weavers in this region. It may be inferred that women weavers are very important in the research area and that treatments should be implemented by government or non-government organizations.

Keywords: *Challenges, Health issue, Problems, Women, Weavers*

*Corresponding Authors:

Dr. Ashalatha K

Professor

Department of Management,

Justice K S Hegde Institute of Management,

Nitte Karkala Taluk, Udupi – 574 110

E-mail: ashalatha@nitte.edu.in, shifasimran03@gmail.com

1. Introduction

With a rich history, the handloom sector is the second largest employer after the agricultural sector. It is one of the oldest. This industry plays a significant role in rural and semi-rural livelihoods because it provides distinct benefits like low power consumption, low capital intensity, eco-friendly production techniques, adaptability in small-scale production, and the ability to innovate and customise products to meet market demands. Handloom weaving, with its decentralised structure, is primarily done by weavers from the lower and middle classes of society. These knowledgeable people meet their domestic demands and make a substantial contribution to the textile industry alongside it. Notably, women actively engage in handloom weaving and are essential in supporting their families monetarily. But the difficulties encountered by female weavers present a complexity picture. They struggle with problems like low pay, health troubles, and a shortage of raw supplies yet playing a crucial role. Due to their lack of resources, many women weavers are unable to access digital banking services. In order to shed light on the nuances of the lives of women weavers in Udupi, this study aims to explore the various issues and difficulties they face. Impact on society and economy, contributes to the wider socio-economic effects of women's handloom weaving participation. Considering how their contributions affect the general well-being of their communities as well as the local economy. Secondly, obstacles to education, the relationship between the educational attainment of female weavers and their financial situation. Finding out how educational obstacles might be a factor in their difficulties. Well-being and Health, investigation of the unique health problems that women weavers encounter, taking into

account the physical strain of their work and the possibility that they may not have access to healthcare. Evaluating the effect on their general well-being and access to healthcare. Evaluate the effect on their general well-being and output. Availability of Raw Materials, analysing the difficulties in obtaining raw materials for handloom weaving. Considering the effects of limited access to high-quality resources on the calibre and volume of their production. Difficulties with Technology, considering the unique technology obstacles that women weavers must overcome, particularly with regard to the use of digital banking services. Examining the obstacles preventing them from utilising technology for financial transactions and consider possible remedies. The Function of Government Policies, investigating how well the current policies of the government assist women weavers. Determining whether the policies in place effectively handle the issues at hand and suggest any improvements that should be made.

This study intends to give a detailed understanding of the difficulties experienced by women weavers in Udupi by carefully investigating these factors. By doing so, it hopes to provide insights that can guide targeted interventions and policy proposals to improve the socioeconomic well-being of these women weavers. In this study an attempt has been made to investigate the level of problems and challenges faced by women weaver in Udupi.

1. Objective

- To understand about the technical support involved in the design input and weaving/dyeing/printing/etc.
- To identify problems faced by women weavers in Udupi District.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Background

Women are having a significant impact across all economic sectors. India has been under lockdown because of COVID-19. It affected women handloom weavers who suffered a severe crisis and lost their means of support.

- Main problems faced by women are lack of working capital, increasing price of raw material, stiff competition from the power loom sector and lack of policy support [1].
- Women weaver suffered from health problems, financial problems and also women weaver are quite dissatisfied with being members in co-operative societies [5].
- While considering the marketing problem- lack of attractive promotion, lack intensive distribution, and lack of customer Relationship management was the severe problem, International Journal of Trade and Commerce, 4(1), 28-33. The handloom industry plays a crucial role in the nation's economy, ranking as the second-largest employer after agriculture. This sector contributes approximately 14% to the country's total cloth production, as per the Annual Report of the Ministry of Textile for 2010-11. In Tamil Nadu, handloom weaving is a significant economic activity, engaging over 1.89 lakh weaver households and 3.19 lakh weavers. Notably, 50% of the state's handloom weavers operate within the cooperative sector, surpassing the national average of 25%. The Handlooms and Textiles Policy Note for 2012-2013 reveals that Tamil Nadu's Handloom Weavers' Cooperative Societies produced 892.22 lakh meters of handloom cloth valued at Rs. 695.08 crore during 2011-2012. These societies sold handloom fabrics amounting to Rs. 852.42 crore, with 824 cooperative societies operating profitably. However, recent trends indicate a decline in the performance of these societies, attributed to various factors impacting weavers, input materials, and marketing challenges [4].
- Majority of weavers are women, and these women experience health issues like leg and back discomfort as well as a shortage of raw materials. The paper brings out the majority of problems in the society as well as physiological problem for women workers during their menstruation, in which they are not permitted to work in the traditional and work place. Even weaving for more than 12 hours a day, they underwent gynecological problems too [2].
- In a research study various problems and challenges faced by the weavers were brought in to notice. It also focuses on the welfare programme conducted by state and central government to promote the handloom product [8]
- "A Socio-Economic Conditions of handloom weaving: A field study in kallidaikurichi of thirunelveli District" detailed on the socio-economic conditions and problems faced by the handloom weavers [3].
- In a research study it is found that education levels of male weavers were more than the female weavers [7].
- The majority of female entrepreneurs are between the ages of 21 and 30. It has also been noted that the majority of them are experiencing financial difficulties. Knowing the issues that women handloom weavers face in this context is crucial [6]. In order to resolve this, we are conducting the research to get more insights on the challenges faced by the women weavers.

3. Research Methodology

In this study, primary data has been obtained using a scheduled interview process. It identified the concerns about the socioeconomic landscape and the difficulties women confront in the handloom industry. In this study Mixed method approach has been used to obtain the data.

Personal interviews had been undertaken in this study to elicit the information.

In this study methodology adopted is Convenience sampling method, Women weavers who live in Udupi Taluk were chosen as a sample. The data has been analyzed using Simple Percentage in Microsoft Excel.

Data sources: The structured questionnaire is prepared to collect the data.

Data collection: Data is collected by face to face interview and through administering the structured questionnaire.

Sampling: A sample of 100 Women weavers are taken into study, from the Taluk of Udupi. Data Analysis: The data is evaluated and analysed using statistical tools- Microsoft excel.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The team of researchers surveyed through personal interviews and structured questions with Women Weavers to know the *Challenges faced by Women Weavers in Udupi District*. A total of 100 respondents are being taken as the sample size in the district.

Data collected has been evaluated and analysed using statistical tool- Microsoft Excel.

i. Challenges and Problem faced by the Respondents

Table 1: Challenges faced by women weavers

Challenges	Respondents	Percentage
Availability of Raw Material	8	8%
Lack of Demand	20	20%
Work-life balance	16	16%
Health issue	32	32%
Traditional stereotype	4	4%
Problems in Marketing product	12	12%
Lack of income during Off-season	8	8%
Total	100	100%

Chart 1: Showing challenges faced by the women Weavers

ii. Interpretation

The above table and chart show's various challenges and problems faced by the women weavers in the Udipi Taluk. Weavers faced the health-related problems because of weaving are 32%. They have been encountered health issues like severe back pain, leg pain, and muscle catch for being continuously involving in weaving. Whereas 20% of the respondents were facing lack of demand for the product in the market. As technology, trends, and changing customer taste and preference were creating lack of demand for the handloomed clothes. Rise of e-commerce platforms were also made constraints to create demand for their products. The weavers found it was difficult to market their product in the current market scenario represented 12% of total sample size. Many of the customers are delighted to go with e-commerce platforms and readymade garments compare to handloomed once. The 16% of the respondents were facing difficulties in managing work life balance. This was caused mainly due to lack of time, where the weavers finding difficult to manage household duties with the weaving. Availability of raw material and lack of income during off season was also remained as a challenge for women weavers, 8% of total sample size faced this problem. Due to variation in the demand and economic downturn it was difficult for the weavers to get access for the raw material. Adding to the above problems 4% of weavers faced traditional stereotyping in their work. There was lack of support from the men in their family. These above-mentioned problems were reacting as a constraint for the weavers to overcome in weaving.

iii. Techniques used in this Research to Rank the Challenges are Henry Garret Ranking

To find out the extent of influence of the challenging factor, Garret Ranking Technique was adopted. Here, Respondents are asked to mention their challenges faced by them. Challenges then ranked from 1 to 7 by 100 respondents.

The Order of challenges are given by the respondents are changed in to percent position by using the following formula.

$$\text{Percent Position} = \frac{100(R_i - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where, R_i is rank given for the i^{th} challenges by j^{th} respondent, N_j is number of challenges ranked by the j^{th} respondent.

Table 2: Ranking of Challenges faced by women weavers

Challenges	Ranks	Formula	Percent position	Garret score	Mean Score
Lack of demand	1	$100(1-0.5)/7$	7.14	78	58.64
Health issue	2	$100(2-0.5)/7$	21.43	65	57.76
Work life balance	3	$100(3-0.5)/7$	35.71	57	56.16
Problems in marketing the product	4	$100(4-0.5)/7$	50	50	50.44
Availability of Raw Material	5	$100(5-0.5)/7$	64.29	42	44.76
Lack of income during offseason	6	$100(6-0.5)/7$	78.57	34	44.48
Traditional stereotype	7	$100(7-0.5)/7$	92.86	22	35.76

Chart 2: Chart showing various Challenges rank

iv. Interpretation

Weavers were asked to rank from 1 to 7 for the challenges faced by them. The above table 2.0 and chart 2.0 shows the mean score which has been calculated from the garret ranking score. The highest mean score has been ranked 1 where mean score = 58.64 represents challenge of lack of demand, weavers were finding difficult to sell their product due to lack of demand in the market. With the changes in the customer trends and preference, in the apparel and fashion handloom products tends to lose their market shares. This factor has majorly impacted even the earnings of the weavers. Rank 2, with the mean score of 57.76 has been factored to health issues faced by the weavers such as back pain, leg pain, muscle catch etc. Rank 3, with the mean score of 56.16 represents the challenges related to work life balance, weavers found difficult to manage weaving with their house hold duties. Rank 4, has been given to problems in marketing the product with the mean score of 50.44, pushing the handloom product to the market was difficult due to lack of accessibility towards customer. Lack of promotional and advertising has kept their product away in the market. There was constraint in budget pertaining to promote their product in the market. Rank 5 has been based on the mean score 44.76 has given to challenges in availing of raw material, weavers were finding difficult to receive raw materials like threads, yarns and other raw material pertaining to weaving. Lack of income during off season was ranked 6 with the mean score of 44.48, weavers were earning less income during off season due to lack of demand in the market to the handloomed products. Traditional stereotype has been ranked 7 with the 35.76 as a mean score, were traditional influence on the gender stereotyping was too least compare to other factors of challenges.

5. Summary of Findings

In the study conducted, it is evident that, weavers are facing numerous challenges and problems such as Availability of raw material, Lack of Demand, work life balance, health issues, traditional stereotype, problems in marketing product and lack of income during off-season. In the above- mentioned challenges, health issues considered to be the majorly faced problem by the women weavers. Health issues pertaining to back pain, leg pain, muscle catch etc. It was also difficult to the weavers to weave during pregnancy. Lack of demand was also another challenge, were weavers found difficult to sell and market their product in the market. The study also discloses the problem of weavers to manage their work life balance. Women weaver were finding difficult to manage house hold duties with the weaving. The both the work was contradicting for them to manage.

With the change in the technology, changing customer taste and preference made the weavers challenging to push their product in to the market.

Study also discloses the changes in the wage payment during the off season to the weavers. Due to lack of income during off season 8% of the total respondent of the sample size found problems in this aspect. 8% of the women weaver faced the problem of traditional stereotyping were there was lack of support to weavers in their family.

6. Suggestion to overcome the problems faced by the Women weavers:

- Marketing of the products can be improved through promotion in the social media in Whatsapp, facebook, Instagram, linkedin.
- Government should organize numerous training programmes to the weavers, so that they can improve their skills in weaving the latest cloth design. Which in return help them to earn more wages.
- In order to avoid competition from mechanized textile sector the government should insist the compulsory usage of handloom mark in the product.
- Government implement special health scheme and welfare schemes to those womens who are involved in weaving, so that women can overcome the burden of expenditure incurred on health related issues.

7. Conclusion

The study sheds light on the challenges faced by women weavers in Udupi Taluk in the handloom sector. These challenges range from health issues and traditional stereotypes to difficulties in marketing products and managing work-life balance. Despite these obstacles, women weavers play a crucial role in their households and contribute significantly to the handloom industry. Irrespective of their education qualification, age, weavers have been possessed with good weaving skill. The major challenge that they faced was health-related. But then the weaving has positively impacted the livelihood of women weavers in Udupi district. Research highlights the need for targeted

interventions and policy proposals to improve the socio-economic well-being of women weavers. It emphasizes the importance of addressing health concerns, improving marketing strategies, and providing support for work-life balance. Additionally, the study underscores the impact of digital financial services on women weavers, suggesting the need for initiatives to enhance their access to such services. The findings point towards the resilience of women weavers who, despite facing various challenges, continue to positively impact their livelihoods through handloom weaving. The study concludes by offering practical suggestions, including promoting products through social media, enhancing skill development programs, and implementing health and welfare schemes to empower women weavers in Udupi. Overall it can be said handloom weaving is more than just making clothing; it's also a means of preserving a portion of history and bringing our ancestors' memories to life.

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